

SGCI Helps Shape SIMIODE Sustainability and More

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ABSTRACT

SIMIODE – Systemic Initiative for Modeling Investigations Using Differential Equations is a non-profit organization devoted to supporting teaching the pivotal STEM course in differential equations using modeling first and throughout.

We describe the rich benefits from SGCI associations, beginning with three members of our team attending the SGCI “Boot Camp” in Indianapolis in May 2019 through our current status post NSF Grant period. SGCI provided SIMIODE with an eye-opening experience for our team and forced us to think about important issues we either wanted to ignore or to which we were oblivious. We returned from the workshop with many good intentions and plans and have worked on a number of them – never enough though, e.g., we conducted a survey of our membership as to how they found us, why they came to us, what keeps them involved, what they like, what they want improved, etc. in which we learned a great deal. We learned about more effective ways to use Analytics and to cold call – although the latter still scares us! We realized a customer viewpoint which often is not natural for the professorate.

Most important, we learned about Sustainability or “What do you do after the grant runs out?” at our sessions in Indianapolis. Some of what we heard was filled with non-traditional words for academics like “sales” and “marketing.” SGCI provided ongoing stimulating consulting which got us to face these realities. We have since taken a fresh look at or initiated three sustainability efforts: (1) SCUDEM – an undergraduate and high school student team challenge which has grown, (2) EXPO – an international virtual conference, and (3) a virtual textbook as a complement to our online OER teaching resources. Currently we are considering developing a SIMIODE MOOC, featuring our virtual text and offering all our OER materials in support of the course.

The memory of discussions surrounding building community are with us and we are still trying to do so, this time with the richer structure and friendlier interfaces of QUBES Hub as we migrate all of SIMIODE – members and resources into QUBES. We valued our sessions on user interfaces and will now incorporate them in our migration of the entire 4,800 member SIMIODE community, hundreds of resources, and community opportunities to QUBES Hub. Once SIMIODE is in the QUBES community we plan to do more focused community building, e.g., we have a high school coordinator and a community college coordinator who are ready to work on engagement activities, and to take advantage of other social and community actions afforded by the rich QUBES community features.

We feel strongly about sharing news of what SGCI has done for our SIMIODE gateway.

Keywords— *sustainability, community, student challenge, virtual conference, virtual textbook, outreach, analytics, membership*

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